

Dual Band Electrochromic Devices based on Nb-doped TiO₂ Nanocrystalline Electrodes

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ABSTRACT

The reliable exploitation of localized surface plasmon resonance in transparent conductive oxides is being prospected to push the blooming of an emerging class of advanced dynamic windows, which offer the opportunity to selectively, and dynamically, control the intensity of the incoming thermal radiation without affecting visible transparency. In this view, Nb-doped TiO₂ colloidal nanocrystals are particularly promising as they have a wide bandgap and their plasmonic features can be finely tailored across the near infrared region, by varying the concentration of dopants. Four batches of Nb-doped TiO₂ nanocrystals with different doping levels (from 0% to 15% of niobium content) have been used here to prepare highly transparent mesoporous electrodes for near-infrared selective electrochromic devices, capable of dynamically modulating the intensity of the transmitted radiation upon the application of a relatively small bias voltage. An engineered dual band electrochromic device (made of 10%_Nb-doped TiO₂ nanocrystals) has been eventually fabricated. It was shown to provide two complementary spectroelectrochemical responses, which can be independently controlled through the intensity of the applied potential: a large variation of the optical transmittance in the near infrared region (by the intensification of the localized surface plasmon scattering) was achievable in the 0-3V voltage window, reaching values greater than 64% in the spectral range from 800 to 2000 nm, whereas the visible absorption could be also intensively varied at higher potentials (from 3V to 4V), driven by Li intercalation into the TiO₂ anatase lattice.

Keywords: Nb-doped TiO₂, colloidal nanocrystals, localized surface plasmon resonance, near infrared selective, dual band, electrochromic devices

The localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) is a long studied nanoscale phenomenon of considerable recent interest, owing to its potential applications in several technological areas such as photocatalysis,^{1,2} optical sensors,^{3,4} and photovoltaics.^{5,6} The vast majority of early investigations of LSPRs has been conducted on noble metals, as they are stable under a wide range of conditions and, especially, as they have a high free electron density.⁷ Later on, during the last fifteen years, the scientific interest in this field has rapidly grown to encompass a broad variety of doped semiconductor nanocrystals (NCs), ranging from metal chalcogenides to wide bandgap transition-metal oxides.⁸⁻¹⁰ Plasmonic features in doped semiconductors are greatly attractive because their resonating energy can be finely tuned by adjusting the concentration of dopants or, in some cases, their off-stoichiometry,^{11,12} thus providing an additional means of tuning the optical properties that is not as readily available in metals, where LSPR peak position can be designed by controlling the NC's size and shape.

It has been recently shown that a considerably large tuning of the LSPR in nanomaterials can be also achieved by reversibly charging/discharging through appropriate electrochemical methods. In other words, it is possible to tune the LSPR response of a given nanomaterial by accumulating or depleting electrons on its surface. At the end of the '90s Mulvaney and co-workers first demonstrated that an electrochemically induced change of the electrons concentration in colloidal Ag nanoparticles resulted in a reversible shift of the LSPR frequency and in a concomitant variation of the optical extinction.¹³⁻¹⁵ The degree of such manipulation is strongly dependent upon the Drude-type free carrier concentration of the plasmonic material: a limited shift of the LSPR is observed in compounds that have a high electron density (i.e., metals, $\sim 10^{23}$ carriers/cm⁻³), as the injection or the removal of even large numbers of electrons results in a small relative change in the carrier concentration. Conversely, materials with a low electron concentration (i.e. doped semiconductors, 10^{16} to 10^{21} carriers/cm⁻³), allow for a much larger modulation of the electron density and, therefore, of the plasmon resonance.

The LSPR of semiconducting NCs can be, in principle, tuned from the terahertz (THz) regime to NIR frequencies, thus providing a versatile tool for a wide range of optoelectronic devices requiring high spectral selectivity.^{9-10, 16-17} The first reliable demonstration of dynamic LSPR tunability in a nanostructured semiconductor was provided in 1999 by Boschloo and Fitzmaurice, who reported an intense and reversible tuning of the optical transmittance in the NIR range associated to the electrochemical doping of an antimony-doped tin oxide (Sb:SnO₂) NCs thin film immersed in a LiClO₄ aqueous solution.¹⁸ This effect was attributed to a purely capacitive charging mechanism and the magnitude of the modulation was shown to depend on the intensity of the applied bias through the film. In 2011 Milliron and co-workers recorded the same behaviour in a film of Tin-doped Indium Oxide (ITO) NCs embedded in a liquid electrolyte, employing a Li/Li⁺ reference electrode.^{19,20} These findings enabled the use of plasmonic semiconductors as active electrodes in an emerging class of electrochromic (EC) devices, which can selectively regulate the optical transmittance in the NIR region without affecting the visible transparency.²¹

To this regard, heavily doped transition-metal oxides are interesting candidates as active materials for NIR-selective EC devices, due to their peculiar optoelectronic properties arising from their outer-d valence electrons.^{22,23} Among them, titanium dioxide (TiO_2) is very attractive because of its high chemical stability and cost-effectiveness as well as of its nontoxicity and earth abundance. Also, TiO_2 is particularly suitable for electrochromic applications because its optoelectronic properties can be conveniently modified by substitutional aliovalent doping: in particular, the substitution of Ti^{4+} by Nb^{5+} cations in TiO_2 has been demonstrated to enhance its electron conductivity making it comparable to that of ITO^{24,25} and to induce the appearance of a LSPR that ranges from the visible (VIS) to the near-infrared (NIR) range.²⁶ Moreover, TiO_2 is a popular lithium insertion material that has been largely employed as pseudocapacitive electrode in lithium-ion batteries.^{27,28} Interestingly, the intercalation of Li^+ ions in TiO_2 produces a visible extinction feature which can be ascribed to a localization of injected electrons on titanium cations, thus creating a polaronic lattice distortion. This phenomenon is similar to the mechanisms proposed for electrochromism in transition-metal oxides, such as WO_x and NbO_x .²⁹ At high intercalation levels, the absorption band associated to the formation of Li_xTiO_2 shifts towards higher energies and covers a broad spectral range in the visible region, as it is well-known from the abundant literature on the optical transition mechanisms occurring in the cathodic EC metal oxides.³⁰

Therefore, TiO_2 NCs can be also reversibly switched between a colourless and a dark state by electrochemical double injection of small alkali metal ions and electrons. Taking advantage of these peculiar properties, Dahlman *et al.*³¹ recently demonstrated the “dual band” dynamic modulation of the optical transmittance in a mesoporous film made of Nb-doped TiO_2 NCs immersed into a Li^+ containing electrolytic solution within a three-electrode set-up. They showed that it may support both LSPR tuning in the NIR and a polaron absorption in the VIS, each of these two phenomena being activated within a specific electrochemical window.

The independent control over the VIS and NIR regions is indeed a key target in the perspective of a reliable development of a next generation of advanced dynamic glazing elements for energy efficient building envelopes. However, until today, an accurate electrochemical investigation, aimed at disentangling the optical response associated to the capacitive charging (which causes the LSPR scattering in the NIR region) from that depending on Li^+ intercalation (responsible for the polaron absorption in the VIS range), has not been reported. Also, the exceptional optical features of these NCs have never been exploited to produce highly efficient and easily up-scalable dual band EC devices, capable of providing two complementary spectro-electrochemical responses that could be independently controlled through the intensity of the external voltage.

Starting from these considerations, we present here a feasible (and easily up-scalable) procedure to fabricate highly transparent mesoporous electrodes made of Nb-doped TiO_2 colloidal building blocks. In particular, we tested four batches of Nb-doped TiO_2 NCs at different Nb loadings, namely 0%, 5%, 10% and

15%. The electrochemical tunability of their LSPR responses has been systematically investigated in a series of lab-scale sandwich-type EC devices and correlated to their most meaningful electrochemical features by means of cyclic voltammetry, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and galvanostatic charging/discharging measurements. A batch of 10%-doped NCs was then employed to fabricate an optimized NIR-selective EC device capable to selectively filter more than 64% of the incoming thermal radiation in the spectral range from 800 to 2000 nm.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Four batches of Nb-doped TiO₂ (NTO) NCs with different Nb content -namely NTO_0 (0% Nb), NTO_5 (5% Nb), NTO_10 (10% Nb) and NTO_15 (15% Nb)- were synthesized by reproducing a previously reported heat-up colloidal synthesis.²⁶ The concentration of niobium in each sample was assessed by ICP elemental analysis. In all the samples the mean NCs size was around 10 nm, as evidenced by TEM analysis, and the crystal structure was TiO₂ anatase (see Electronic Supporting Information, **Figure S1** and **S3a**). These colloidal NCs were used to fabricate a series of mesoporous films to be used as active electrodes for NIR selective EC devices. In order to provide high EC performances, such electrodes must fulfil four fundamental requirements: 1) high transparency both in the VIS and in the NIR range, 2) large surface area, 3) good electronic conductivity and 4) efficient charge injection at relatively low bias potentials. To fulfil these requirements, each batch of NTO NCs was turned into a suitably viscous paste and deposited by screen-printing onto a set of ITO-coated glass substrates. The films were then subjected to a programmed sequence of annealing steps in air up to 430 °C. The native organic ligands, which still surround the NCs at the initial stages of the thermal treatment, play a pivotal role in the preservation of the NCs shape and size (preventing them to sinter together) and in the formation of homogeneous NCs films. As it can be seen in **Figure 1**, which shows the SEM image of a mesoporous electrode prepared from NTO_10 NCs, the initial morphology of the nanocrystalline building blocks was adequately preserved through the post-synthetic processing, and the annealed NCs were well-dispersed and homogeneously distributed over the whole cross-section of the film (see also **Figure S1** for comparison). The XRD analysis of the resulting films (see **Figures S3**) revealed not only that the TiO₂ body-centred tetragonal anatase crystal structure of the starting NCs was preserved, but also that no evident sintering occurred, as attested from the calculation of the lattice parameters before and after the thermal treatment, which are reported in **Table S1**.

Thereafter, while the structural and morphological properties of NTO NCs were maintained upon the preparation of the mesoporous electrodes, their optical features were found to change: the diluted Nb-doped TiO₂ NCs showed a characteristic LSPR feature around 2500 nm, whereas the corresponding thermally treated dense mesoporous films did not exhibit any detectable optical feature in that spectral window (see **Figure 2a**). This effect may be tentatively associated to the superficial oxidation of the NCs upon removal of the oleic capping layer, and, thus, to a consistent reduction of the overall free electron density. Another

possible explanation could be that the annealing produced a continuous 3D mesoporous network upon “necking” of neighboring NCs with a drastic decrease of the overall surface-to-volume ratio with respect to the case of suspended (isolated) building blocks. Both effects are plausible and may work concertedly in reducing the average electron density. Moreover, grain boundaries at the interface between different nanocrystalline domains may act as shallow electron trapping sites,^{32,33} further contributing to depress the LSPR features.

These four batches of NTO mesoporous electrodes exhibited high transparency in the visible range, as shown in **Figure 2b**: the optical transmittance at 550 nm ranged from 83% of NTO_15 to 88% for NTO_0, while the average reflectance was lower than 10% in all the films. They can be thus used profitably as transparent electrodes over the whole spectral range that is affected by the optical modulation, as they guarantee high transparency in their bleached state. Moreover, a clear widening of the band-gap associated to the higher Nb content in the NCs (known as the Burstein-Moss effect) was already observed in the case of suspended NCs.²⁶ This remained valid in the corresponding NTO mesoporous electrodes: the Tauc plots, shown in the inset of **Figure 2b**, reveal indeed a coherent blue-shift of the optical absorption from the onset value of 3.39 eV of the film NTO_0 to 3.52 eV of NTO_15.

To measure the entity of shift in the Fermi level among the four NTO electrodes, a first run of EIS measurements was carried out in a three-electrode set-up in a 0.5M Na₂SO₃ aqueous solution. By fitting the values of the space-charge capacitance, C_{SC}, in a frequency range corresponding to the capacitive response of the film, we traced the Mott–Schottky plots of these four NTO mesoporous films (see **Figure 2c**). The values of the intercept with the x-axis were used to sketch a qualitative trend in the variation of the flat-band potential V_{FB}.^{34,35} As expected, at higher Nb concentrations a shift towards more positive potentials was observed, with a difference between V_{FB} of NTO_0 and V_{FB} of NTO_x varying from ~150 meV for x=5 to ~220 meV for x=15.

The average carrier density (N_D) in each electrode was estimated from the slope of the linear segment fitting the values of the capacitance measured at higher negative potentials.³⁶ Upon assigning the appropriate numbers to all the parameters that appear in the Mott-Schottky equation, we found that N_D increased from 7.8×10¹⁸ cm⁻³ in NTO_0 to 1.3×10¹⁹ cm⁻³ in NTO_10. Surprisingly, no further enhancement was detected in NTO_15 electrodes, perhaps as a consequence of incipient segregation phenomena that detrimentally affected the electron mobility in this the semiconductor.³⁷

These results have been used to draw a meaningful trend of the intensity of the applied potential necessary to induce the formation of an accumulation layer among the different batches of mesoporous semiconductors. It should be remarked, however, that the values of V_{FB} and N_D have been extrapolated from the Mott-Schottky equation upon making some simplified assumptions, which do not entirely hold in the case of a mesoporous film.³⁴ In the ESI section we report the full set of EIS data used to extrapolate the Mott-Schottky plots of NTO_0 and NTO_10 films (together with that of a bare ITO-glass substrate as

reference), along with a detailed explanation of the empirical assumptions made to extrapolate the above referred numbers (see **Figure S6**).

A set of 1 μ m-thick NTO electrodes was then used to prepare a series of lab-scale EC devices, for which we employed a 1M solution of 1,2-dimethyl-3-propylimidazolium iodide (DMPII) in propylene carbonate (PC) as electrolyte and a thin Pt layer (deposited on ITO glass) as counter electrode. A sandwich cell made by two ITO glasses filled with the electrolytic solution was used as the reference cell in all the measurements. The choice of DMPII mainly relies on the size of cations in this electrolyte, which are too large to intercalate into TiO₂. This prevents the observation of optical transitions from the bulk material, guaranteeing at the same time only the activation of the spectro-electrochemical response connected to surface charging mechanisms, which drive the modulation of the LSPR intensity. On the other hand, the use of iodide as counter ion triggers a redox reaction at the Pt counter electrode, making a considerable faradic current available to charge the electrode.

The transmittance spectra of these NTO-based EC devices are reported in **Figure 3** for a given set of applied bias potentials, whereas the corresponding optical extinction spectra are provided in **Figure S4**. The electrode made of TiO₂ NCs (NTO_0) showed only a modest optical modulation at wavelengths above 1500 nm: the overall ΔT_{NIR} was 14% (calculated in the range from 800 to 2700) with a maximum ΔT of 35% at 2700 nm, when applying a 1.6V negative potential. EC cells based on NTO_5 and NTO_10 NCs exhibited instead a much larger variation of the optical transmittance in the NIR, resulting in an overall ΔT_{NIR} of 70% and a maximum ΔT of 85% at wavelengths above 2000 nm in the case of NTO_10, without any significant variation of the transparency in the visible. On the other hand, the maximum optical modulation achievable by the NTO_15-based electrode was consistently lower than that made of NTO_10 NCs, confirming, once again, that the raise in the Nb concentration from 10% to 15% did not lead to an increase of the overall free electron density. As it is possible to appreciate from **Figure 4**, where the most meaningful spectral features of NTO_0-, NTO_5- and NTO_10-based electrodes have been summarized, NTO_10 displayed the largest optical modulation, which was more than twice higher than that of NTO_5. The intensification of the optical density (OD) in this sample was also found to vary linearly with the applied voltage (see **Figure 4a**), suggesting that a further increment should be even possible at higher potentials. Conversely, NTO_0 and NTO_5 exhibited a limited intensification of the OD, reaching a saturation point at a voltage between 1.5V and 1.6V.

The spectral distribution of ΔT in the same electrochemical window (namely 0V - 1.6V) is plotted in **Figure 4b**: the wavelength corresponding to the maximum ΔT , namely $\lambda_{\text{LSPR_MAX}}$, was observed to consistently blue-shift as the amount of Nb dopant increased from 0% to 10%, reaching 2300 nm at 10% concentration. These results confirmed that the availability of a larger number of free carriers in NTO NCs, with respect to undoped TiO₂ NCs, led to a wider tunability of the OD and to a generalized lowering of the onset potential, in accordance with the variation of V_{FB} position depicted in **Figure 2c**.

To better correlate the above displayed LSPR features to the charge storage properties of these electrodes, a second run of electrochemical measurements in a three-electrode set-up was carried out, using a 1M LiClO₄ in propylene carbonate as electrolyte solution. In **Figure 5a** we report the cyclic voltammograms of the whole set of NTO electrodes scanned at 1mV/s. All the electrodes show a well-resolved reduction peak at -1.25V vs. Ag/AgCl corresponding to the phase transition from tetragonal TiO₂ anatase to orthorhombic Li_xTiO₂.^[38-39] The intensity of the Li⁺ insertion/deinsertion peak decreased with increasing Nb concentration in the NCs, with the bare TiO₂ NCs exhibiting the most intense peak. This effect can be reasonably associated to the greater lattice hindrance to Li⁺ insertion caused by the electrostatic repulsion exercised by Nb⁵⁺ ions that replaced Ti⁴⁺ cations in NTO NCs.⁴⁵ As a further confirmation of this trend, the galvanostatic charging/discharging profiles measured at 0.1C current rate highlighted the superior Li-storage of undoped TiO₂ NCs (see **Figure 5b**).

We also performed a second run of EIS measurements (in 1M LiClO₄ in propylene carbonate) to investigate the effect of Nb-doping on both charge transfer and charge transport phenomena occurring during the intercalation process. The Nyquist plots of NTO_0, NTO_5 and NTO_10 electrodes measured under different bias conditions (from -0.75V to -1.00 V) are reported in **Figure S8**. The EIS spectra of the four electrodes measured at -1V are plotted in **Figure 5c**. All the curves exhibit a depressed semicircle at high frequencies accompanied by a linear segment at lower frequencies. The x-axis intercept in the high frequency region provides a semi-quantitative information on the overall bulk resistance of the electrode, which was found to slightly decrease at higher doping levels. The pronounced semicircle at high-to-medium (10 - 50000 Hz) frequencies is ascribable to the charge-transfer phenomena, whereas the straight line corresponding to low/medium frequency range (around 0.1-10 Hz) corresponds to semi-infinite Warburg impedance. The slope of this line is observed to decrease upon Li⁺ insertion. The steep sloping line at even lower frequencies (0.01 - 0.1 Hz) is instead ascribable to the finite-space diffusion process, namely to the intercalation capacitance. Upon fitting all the EIS spectra through the equivalent circuit model showed in the inset of **Figure 5c**,⁴⁰ it was possible to estimate the values of the charge transfer resistance, R_{ct}, and of the lithium diffusion coefficient, D_{Li+}, at different bias voltages (see **Figure 5d** and **5e**). The latter is observed to undergo a considerable drop in the doped electrodes, with a difference of almost one order of magnitude, detectable at -1V, between NTO_0 and NTO_15.

These results clearly evidence that Nb dopants have two opposite effects on the charge storage prerogatives of these TiO₂ mesoporous electrodes: on one side they allow for an increment of the overall electron density and for the consequent enhancement of the surface capacitance (as indirectly attested by the intensification of the LSPR scattering); on the other side they reduce the contribution of the Li-diffusion, leading, consequently, to a generalized reduction of the bulk (or diffusion related) capacitance.

With such findings in mind, we attempted to fabricate an optimized dual band EC device, which is capable of maximizing the intensity of optical modulation of the Nb-doped titanium oxide both in the NIR (through

LSPR scattering) and in the VIS region (through polaron absorption). NTO_10 NCs, which exhibited the best EC performance in the NIR region, were thus employed in the preparation of a highly transparent mesoporous electrode having a thickness of 2.1 μm . A 50 μm thick hot-melt SurlynTM gasket was used as a sealant and a specific Li-based electrolyte, composed of 0.1M LiI + 1M LiCl in dimethylsulfoxide, was used to fill the cell. The addition of such small amount of LiI was demonstrated, indeed, to foster the building-up of a deeper charge accumulation layer at the interface with the mesoporous electrode, which translated into a much stronger optical attenuation in the NIR region.⁴¹

The transmittance spectra of the EC device are reported in **Figure 6a** for a given set of applied potentials (in the range from 0V to -4V). Under the application of a moderate cathodic potential (up to -3V), an outstandingly large modulation of the optical transmittance in the NIR range, ΔT_{NIR} , was recorded (average $\Delta T_{\text{NIR}} \sim 53\%$, $\Delta T_{\text{MAX}} = 67\%$ at 2000 nm) in face of only a modest reduction of the VIS transparency, which was rather ascribable to the formation of oxidized iodide species in the electrolyte. At these voltages Li^+ ions did not deeply intercalate into the TiO_2 lattice, but most likely they accumulated around the NCs surface to balance the increased semiconductor's electron concentration. A consistent reduction of the optical transmittance in the VIS range became instead observable at higher applied potentials (from -3V to -4V), as an effect of the intense polaron absorption associated to the massive Li^+ insertion occurring at these potentials.⁴² At -4V the incident radiation was almost completely shielded within the whole measured spectral range.

The time-resolved variation of the optical transmittance upon the application of a square-wave switching potential is shown in **Figure 6b** at three different wavelengths, that are 550 nm (@ -4V/+1V), 750 nm (@ -4V/+1V) and 2000 nm (@ -3V/+1V) respectively: the coloring time, t_c (which is here measured as the time to get 90% of ΔT_{MAX} at a certain wavelength) was found to range from ~ 10 s at 2000 nm up to ~ 105 s at 500 nm, while the corresponding current density flowing into the EC layer was in the order of 1-2 mA/cm^2 . Eventually, the medium-term electrochemical stability of this EC device was also assessed by running a series of 200 charging/discharging cycles: the first and the 200th voltammetry scans are reported in **Figure 6c**.

These results highlight the possibility to independently activate two different optical responses in an NTO-based EC device by controlling two electrochemical processes which lay at the basis of charge accumulation on the active electrode, namely one driven by the double-layer surface capacitance and one driven by Li^+ insertion and bulk capacitance. As already observed by Dahlman *et al.* over an analysis conducted in a three-electrode set-up,³¹ the first process is associated to the intensification of the LSPR scattering (and it is characterized by a relatively fast switching time), whereas the second manifests as optical absorption at higher potentials (and is characterized by a much longer switching time).

As previously mentioned, NIR electrochromism is of particular interest in the field of energy efficient glass façades due to the fascinating perspective of admitting as much daylight as possible while conveniently

regulating the thermal radiation passing through the window. In this regard, to adequately assess the impact of the here presented EC system in this sector, two fundamental figures of merit, which are generally adopted to define the optical features of a glazing element, were calculated: i) the overall solar energy transmittance in the range 350-2000 nm, denoted as T_{SOL} ; and ii) the luminous transmittance in the range 400-700 nm, denoted as T_{LUM} . T_{SOL} and T_{LUM} were calculated by averaging the optical transmittance over the solar irradiance at air mass 1.5 φ_{SOL} (in accordance with the DIN EN 410⁴³) and to the eye's photopic luminous efficiency function φ_{LUM} (in accordance with the CIE standards⁴⁴):

$$T_{SOL/LUM} = \frac{\int T(\lambda)\varphi_{SOL/LUM}d\lambda}{\int \varphi_{SOL/LUM}d\lambda} \quad (1)$$

The variation of T_{SOL} , T_{LUM} and T_{NIR} as a function of the applied external voltage in our EC device is plotted in **Figure 6d**. The turning point, found at around -3V, corresponds to an abrupt change of both the slope of T_{LUM} the maximum value of T_{LUM}/T_{SOL} , namely 1.54. At higher potentials the VIS transmittance was dramatically lowered to the minimum value of T_{LUM} (~7%), recorded in correspondence of the highest tolerable bias potential. These results eventually underscore the possibility to effectively regulate the spectral response offered by the here referred EC systems.

CONCLUSIONS

Dynamic modulation of the LSPR scattering in Nb-TiO₂ colloidal NCs has been exploited in a set of engineered mesoporous electrodes capable of selectively controlling the intensity of NIR radiation transmitted through a double-glazed electrochemical device filled with a redox electrolyte. Having systematically investigated the spectroelectrochemical signatures of four different batches of colloidal NCs, we could evaluate the effect of Nb doping on their charge accommodation characteristics. Using NTO NCs containing 10% of Nb, which exhibited the best performances, we have ultimately fabricated a dual band EC device that allows for selectively filtering out the NIR radiation at applied potentials lower than 3V, or for cutting down both VIS and NIR transmittance at applied potentials higher than 3V. The experimental achievements presented here offer greatly expanding options to the development of a next generation of dynamic glazed building facades, which are prospected to maximize both thermal and visual comfort at any climatic condition while reducing the overall energy use and environmental impact.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials. Titanium(IV) ethoxide (TEO), Niobium(V) Chloride (NbCl₅, 99%), 1-Octadecanol (ODAL, 99%), Oleic Acid (OAc, 90%), 1-Octadecene (ODE, 90%), hexane and acetone were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Synthesis of Nb-doped TiO₂ NCs. Recent advances in wet-chemistry routes have enabled the preparation of a large spectrum of engineered TiO₂ NCs whose crystallographic features can be finely controlled during the crystal growth process.^{38,45,46} In this study, both Nb-doped and pure TiO₂ anatase NCs were synthesized using the procedure reported by De Trizio *et al.*²⁶ All the reactions were carried out under nitrogen using standard air-free techniques. In a typical synthesis a mixture of octadecanol (ODAL) (13 mmol), oleic acid (OAc) (1 mmol), and octadecene (ODE) (4 mL) was degassed under vacuum at 120 °C for 1 h in a three-neck flask. In a second flask, titanium ethoxide (TEO) (1 mmol), ODE (1 mL) and the desired amount of NbCl₅ were mixed together under inert atmosphere and then heated up to 80 °C for 1h to get a clear solution. This solution, once cooled to room temperature, was subsequently injected, with a syringe, into the first reaction flask under nitrogen flow at 100°C. The temperature was then raised to 290 °C for 60 min to let the NCs grow. The reaction was quenched by cooling the reaction flask to room temperature and the NCs were cleaned by precipitation with acetone and redispersion in hexane. This last step was repeated three times. At each washing step, 100 μL of OAc were added to the NC solution to prevent aggregation. Finally, the NCs were dispersed in 4 mL of toluene and 25 μL of OAc to yield a stable colloidal solution. Four different samples were prepared by varying the amount of the Nb precursor from 0% to 15%, while keeping the amount of Ti precursor fixed.

TEM measurements. The samples were prepared by dropping dilute solutions of NCs onto carbon coated gold grids, which were then placed under vacuum to preserve them from oxidation. Low-resolution transmission electron microscopy (TEM) measurements were carried out on a JEOL JEM-1100 transmission electron microscope operating at an accelerating voltage of 100 kV.

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) measurements. The XRD analysis was performed on a PANalytical Empyrean X-ray diffractometer equipped with a 1.8 kW CuKα ceramic X-ray tube, PIXcel^{3D} 2x2 area detector and operating at 45 kV and 40 mA. Specimens for the XRD measurements were prepared in a glove box by dropping a concentrated NCs solution onto a quartz zero-diffraction single crystal substrate. The diffraction patterns were collected at ambient conditions using a parallel beam geometry and symmetric reflection mode. XRD data analysis was carried out using the HighScore 4.1 software from PANalytical.

Elemental Analysis. This was carried out *via* Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-AES), using an iCAP 6500 Thermo spectrometer. Samples were dissolved in HCl/HNO₃ 3:1 (v/v) at 80°C for 24h. All chemical analyses performed by ICP-AES were affected by a systematic error of about 5%.

Fabrication of NIR-selective EC cells. 3x2 cm² ITO-coated glass samples (size: 3 x 2 cm², thickness: 1.1 mm, resistivity: 20 Ω/sq, from XIN YAN TECHNOLOGY LTD) were used as substrates for the fabrication of Nb-TiO₂ electrodes. The substrates were cleaned up *via* three subsequent sonication steps in deionized water, acetone and isopropanol. Pristine colloidal NCs suspended in toluene were turned into printable viscous pastes upon the addition of a proper amount of ethyl cellulose (30-70 mPa*s from Sigma Aldrich)

dissolved in a mix of ethanol and α -terpineol. Low boiling solvents were then let slowly evaporated through a R-300 Rotavapor[®]. Mesoporous electrodes were obtained by depositing the Nb-TiO₂-containing viscous pastes by screen-printing and then subjecting the films to thermal annealing in air 430°C for 30min. The deposition process was repeated several times until the desired thickness was achieved. The films have been observed through a FEI Helios 600i electron beam system and then used as active electrodes in hybrid-type sandwich EC cells having a 1 cm² active area. A thin Platinum layer (< 5nm) –also prepared by doctor blade (from Dyesol[™] PT1 viscous paste) and subsequent thermal treatment at 430°C on ITO substrate- was used as counter electrode. The choice of ITO as transparent conductive underlayer was driven by the necessity to guarantee an high optical transmission over the full range of wavelengths covered in this work (namely from 300 nm to 2500 nm). Upon thermal annealing at 430°C the ITO-coated glass exhibited a high transmittance (averagely >82%) over both VIS and NIR regions, at the cost of a tolerable reduction of the electron conductivity (the sheet resistance increased from ~20 Ω /sq to ~85 Ω /sq). A thermoplastic gasket was used as sealant. The electrolyte was introduced into the cell gap through a hole that had been predrilled on the back of the Pt-coated glass. The hole was finally sealed with a thermosetting resin.

Optical characterization. Optical transmittance (T%) and reflectance (R%) spectra in the range from 350 to 2500nm were measured with a Varian[®] Cary 5000 spectrophotometer equipped with an integrating sphere. The optical absorption coefficient (α) was determined through the following equation ⁴⁷

$$T = \frac{(1-R)^2 e^{-\alpha d}}{1-R^2 \cdot e^{-2\alpha d}} \quad (2)$$

where d is the thickness of the film, T and R are the film transmittance and reflectance, respectively, both corrected by the substrate characteristics (glass, in this case). The type and energy of inter-band transitions could be estimated by linear fitting of $(\alpha h\nu)^n$ (Tauc plots), in this case $n = 1/2$ because TiO₂ is an indirect bandgap semiconductor.⁴⁸

Electrochemical characterization. All the electrochemical measurements were carried out in a three-electrode set-up by using an AUTOLAB PGSTAT302N potentiostat provided with a FRAII integrated impedance module. NTO films (deposited on ITO) were used as working electrodes, while a Platinum foil was chosen as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl as reference electrode. In the run of Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements aimed at determining the space charge layer capacitance C_{sc} , we performed AC modulated cyclic voltage scans in a 0.5 M Na₂SO₃ aqueous solution (pH ~9) in a range of frequencies comprised between 0.01 Hz and 100 KHz, under dark conditions. The capacitance of the space charge layer was calculated by assuming:³⁶

$$C \sim C_{sc} = 1/|\omega Z_{im}| \quad (3)$$

where Z_{im} is the imaginary part of the measured impedance.

In order to determine the flat band potential, the capacitance of the space charge layer was calculated from the imaginary part of the impedance. The dependence of C_{SC} on the bias potential (V) is described by the Mott-Schottky equation:³⁶

$$\frac{1}{C_{SC}^2} = \left(\frac{2}{\epsilon_R \epsilon_0 N_D e_0} \right) \left([V - V_{FB}] - \frac{k_B T}{e_0} \right) \quad (4)$$

where C_{SC} is the measured differential capacitance per area unit, e_0 is the elementary charge, ϵ_R is the dielectric constant of the semiconductor, ϵ_0 is the electrical permittivity of vacuum, N_D is density of donor atoms in the semiconductor, V is the applied bias potential in volts, k_B is Boltzmann's constant, e the electron charge and T is the temperature (298 K). Therefore, from the C_{SC}^{-2} vs. V plot, V_{FB} can be extracted from the intercept with the x-axis.³⁶

In the run of galvanostatic (charge/discharge), cyclic voltammetry and EIS measurements aimed at evaluating the Li insertion prerogatives of the NTO films, 1M solution of LiClO_4 in propylene carbonate was used as electrolyte (again in a three-electrode set-up with Pt as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl as reference electrode). EIS spectra were fitted through the equivalent circuit model showed in the inset of **Figure 5c** composed of a series resistance element (R_b), an high-frequency charge-transfer resistance element (R_{CT}), a constant phase element (C_{DL}), which accounted for both the intercalation capacitance (in the medium-frequency domain) and the double layer capacitance (in quasi-equilibrium regime) and a finite space Warburg element Z_{FLW} , which accounts for the solid-state diffusion of Li^+ ions into the thin oxide layer, C_{INT} which account for intercalation capacitance.⁴⁰

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

The Supporting Information file is available free of charge is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI: 10.1021/acsnano.xxxxxx. It provides the following additional data:

- TEM images of the as-synthesized NTO colloidal NCs
- Transmittance spectra of an NTO_10 film upon three different thermal treatment conditions
- Mott-Schottky plots at different applied potentials
- BET analysis of the NTO_10 film
- Optical extinction spectra of the NTO films at different applied potentials
- Nyquist plots of the NTO films measured in a three-electrode setup within a 1M LiClO_4 solution

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Figure 1. SEM images of an NTO_10 electrode upon thermal annealing at 430°C, a) top view and b) cross-sectional view.

Figure 2. a) Absorption spectra of NTO_0, NTO_5, NTO_10 and NTO_15 NCs in suspended toluene (inset) and of the mesoporous films obtained from of the same NCs after the thermal sintering at 430°C in air. b) Transmittance spectra of the same films and the inherent Tauc plots (inset). c) Mott-Schottky plots of the same mesoporous electrodes at 23 Hz

Figure 3. Transmission spectra of the NTO_0, NTO_5, NTO_10 and NTO_15 electrodes at different bias voltages.

Figure 4. a) Variation of the optical density at 2500 nm in the range from -1.0V to -1.6V; b) spectral variation of the optical transmittance (ΔT) at -1.6V.

Figure 5. a) Cyclic voltammetry, b) galvanostatic charging/discharging measurements and c) Nyquist plots (at -1V) of the four investigated batches of NTO electrodes. All the measurements have been performed in a three-electrode setup (with a Platinum foil as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl as reference electrode) using 1M LiClO₄ in propylene carbonate as electrolyte. The values of d) R_{CT} and e) D_{Li+} as a function of the applied potential have been extrapolated upon fitting EIS data through the equivalent circuit model showed in the inset of Figure 5c.

Figure 6. Spectroelectrochemical features of an EC device embodying a 2.1 μm-thick NTO₁₀ electrode: a) transmittance spectra at different bias potentials in the range 0/-4V; b) time variation of the optical transmittance at 500, 750 and 2000 nm ; c) cyclic voltammetry plots of the EC device measured at a scan rate of 1mV/sec; d) variation of the average value of T_{SOL}, T_{LUM} and T_{NIR} with the intensity of applied potential.